

Research Article

Description of Hemoglobin Agarose Gel Electrophoresis Bands in Newborns, Diabetes Mellitus and Normal Individuals

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Abstract

Background: Normal adult human haemoglobin consists of two main types, namely HbA, HbF, and HbA2. HbF is present in newborns until the age of 6 months, and is the main haemoglobin in infant red blood cells. Haemoglobin in patients with diabetes mellitus (haemoglobinopathy) is predicted to have haemoglobin S (HbS), haemoglobin C (HbC), or haemoglobin E (HbE). In this study, the presence of Hb in DM patients was examined to determine whether its migration position was close to HbA and HbA2.

Objective: To determine the differences in the band pattern of the haemoglobin electrophoresis method in newborns, patients with diabetes mellitus, and normal individuals.

Methods: This study used an exploratory experimental design. The instrument used was horizontal electrophoresis with agarose gel. The specimens were EDTA blood from newborn infants, individuals with diabetes mellitus, and normal individuals. Thirteen haemolysates could be applied to the electrophoresis instrument simultaneously, and the patterns could be observed after staining with Coomassie Brilliant Blue (CBB) for 60 minutes at a constant speed of 100 mA.

Results: Newborns have only one band, namely HbF, people with diabetes mellitus also have one band parallel to the HbF band, and normal individuals (adults) have two bands, namely HbA and HbA2 (thin) and thick.

Conclusion: Hb in adults/normal individuals is the smallest (HbA), because it migrates to the positive pole faster than Hb in newborns (HbF) and individuals with diabetes mellitus (HbF). Hb in individuals with diabetes mellitus is glycosylated by glucose molecules, making it heavier, so that HbA becomes HbF.

1. Introduction

The prognosis for diabetes mellitus is the result of an HbA1c test, which measures glycosylated haemoglobin, described as haemoglobin A1c (HbA1c). HbA1c is a glycaemic control marker used to monitor and predict the risk of complications in patients with diabetes mellitus (DM). HbA1c levels reflect the average glucose concentration over the past 2–3 months. Several HbA1c measurement methods with different limitations and advantages are available, such as: capillary electrophoresis (CE) [1], high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), and turbidimetric immunoinhibition assays.

In Hb electrophoresis results, many factors can affect haemoglobin bands, such as blood transfusions, bleeding, iron deficiency, anaemia, and red blood cell half-life, which are considered to affect HbA1c measurements [2], resulting in very low HbA1c levels, thus ruling out diabetes mellitus. The frequency and distribution of haemoglobinopathies among different countries are usually associated with Hb related to

sickle cell anaemia (HbS) [3]. HbE bands are often found in haemoglobinopathy patients in Bangladesh, Myanmar, East Asia and Southeast Asia.

Research on haemoglobinopathy patients with diabetes mellitus reviewed from Hb variants found only one-third of all patients. Thalassaemia is a haemoglobinopathy with varying frequencies among different regions, from 3–9% for β -thalassaemia [4], 20–30% for α -thalassaemia, and 10–60% for the HbE phenotype [5]. The prevalence of haemoglobinopathy (thalassaemia) carriers in Indonesia is estimated to be around 3–8%, or approximately 3,000 babies with thalassaemia born each year, making Indonesia one of the countries with the highest prevalence in Southeast Asia. There are more than 30 types of mutations found, with 2,500 babies with thalassaemia born per year. Based on the high prevalence of Hb variants in the Indonesian population, this can lead to misinterpretation of HbA1c results [6].

The main difference between adult Hb (HbA) and Hb in newborns (HbF) is in the type of chains that make them up to 6 HbA (adult haemoglobin) consists of two alpha chains and two beta chains, while HbF (foetal haemoglobin) consists of two alpha chains and two gamma chains [7]. In individuals with diabetes mellitus, glycated haemoglobin (to which glucose molecules are attached) increases the molecular weight of Hb [8].

Based on the high prevalence of Hb variants in several countries, which causes misinterpretation of HbA1c results [9], this study was conducted to investigate whether Hb variants in patients with diabetes mellitus in Hb electrophoresis have shifted from the HbA band to a band similar to that found in newborns (HbF) [8].

2. Research Method

The design of this study is exploratory experimental. The population and sample used research groups consisting of 5 normal individual respondents, 5 newborn respondents [10], and 5 respondents with diabetes mellitus [11]. For DM patients, the inclusion criteria were patients with HbA1c levels $> 6.5\%$. All samples were obtained from Surabaya Medical Service Hospital [12].

Research materials and equipment

A. Alkaline Electrophoresis Buffer Recipe (pH 8.6) [13]

Tris-Borate-EDTA (TBE) Buffer pH 8.6 (5X) (Concentrate, 1 litre) [14]

R/ Tris Base \rightarrow 54 grams

Boric Acid \rightarrow 27.5 grams

EDTA (Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid), pH 8.0 \rightarrow 3.72 grams

Distilled water \rightarrow up to 1 litre

B. Hemolyzing Solution Recipe

R/ Saponin: 1 gram

EDTA (Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid), pH 8.0: 0.1 M (optional, for Hb stabilization)

Tris-HCl Buffer, pH 7.0 – 8.5: 10 mM

NaCl (Sodium Chloride): 150 mM

Distilled water: up to 100 mL

C. Fixative Reagent: Iso-propanol solution

D. Staining Reagent: Coomassie brilliant blue G-250

R/ 10% (v/v) acetic acid/0.006%, Methanol 50% (w/v) Coomassie brilliant blue G- 250 (Bio-Rad), store for several months at room temperature.

E. Washing solution: 10% acetic acid.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Overview of Hemoglobin Electrophoresis Results (as Control)

Hemoglobin electrophoresis should always be interpreted in consideration of the patient's clinical picture, such as:

1. When considering a low mean corpuscular volume (MCV), iron deficiency anemia should be excluded in the evaluation of the patient.
2. If there is no iron deficiency anemia and the MCV is low, the presence of HbS should be suspected as HbS/ β thalassemia syndrome.
3. Therefore, if the patient does not produce β -globin chains, such as in HbSS/HbSC and HbS β 0 disease, they will not have HbA [13].

3.2. Hemoglobin Electrophoresis Results in Normal Individuals

Thalassemia minor (also known as beta thalassemia trait or carrier) is a mild condition in which a person inherits one copy of the gene that causes beta thalassemia, but has no symptoms and does not require treatment [17].

In beta-thalassemia, the electrophoresis pattern differs between the major and minor forms. Beta-thalassemia minor shows a slight decrease in HbA and a slight increase in HbA₂, while beta-thalassemia major shows a severe decrease or loss of HbA, but a significant increase in HbF and HbA₂ [13].

In alpha-thalassemia, HbH (beta-globin chain tetramer) or Hb Barts (gamma-globin chain tetramer) can be identified. This finding is not seen in beta-thalassemia [18].

Beta-thalassemia is characterized by increased production of HbA₂. Therefore, in HbS/beta-thalassemia syndrome, there will be an increase in HbA₂ production. These patients also tend to have microcytic and hypochromic erythrocytes [19].

Figure 1: Agarose gel electrophoresis shows Band 1: Control (hemoglobin marker band) with HbA, HbF, HbS, and HbA2, Band 2: sickle cell patient sample showing faint HbA, HbF, and HbA2. Band 3: newborn sample with only HbF. Band 4: normal individual sample with HbA and HbA2 (<3%)

Figure 2: Hemoglobin electrophoresis results in normal adults, visible in bands 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 9, 11, and 12 HbA and thin HbA2 bands (due to very low levels), but in bands 10 and 11 [15], HbA is very thick, suggesting that the individual has beta thalassemia minor [16]

3.3. Hemoglobin Electrophoresis Results in Newborns

Figure 3: Hemoglobin electrophoresis results in newborns on bands 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 9, 10, 11, 12 are HbF [20]

Newborns normally have high levels of hemoglobin F (HbF) (50-80%) which decrease over time, while hemoglobin A (HbA) levels begin to increase. This test is important for detecting hemoglobin abnormalities that can cause anemia and other serious conditions. Hemoglobin in newborns is HbF (fetal hemoglobin) because HbF has a higher affinity for oxygen than HbA (adult hemoglobin), thereby facilitating oxygen transfer from the mother to the fetus through the placenta. The different structure of HbF allows the fetus to obtain oxygen from the lower oxygen pressure in the mother's placental blood vessels, which then helps the fetus grow and develop properly in the womb. Therefore, HbF likely has a higher molecular weight than HbA, enabling it to store more oxygen in the mother's placenta.

3.4. Hemoglobin Electrophoresis Results in Patients with Diabetes Mellitus

Figure 4: Bands 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, normal individuals with HbA, bands 7, 8, 9, newborns with HbF, and bands 10, 11, 12 are bands of individuals with diabetes mellitus, namely HbF [21]

HbA1c is the most widely used analyte for measuring average glycemic control. HbA1c is a measure of the percentage of hemoglobin molecules bound to glucose. The higher the glucose concentration over the past 2-3 months, the higher the HbA1c level. The HbA1c test is used to monitor the average glucose concentration of patients diagnosed with diabetes, and if it increases, it can be used to diagnose diabetes.

Hemoglobinopathies are often associated with artificially altered hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) concentrations. The term “hemoglobinopathy” encompasses all genetic hemoglobin disorders. There are two main types of hemoglobinopathies: (1) thalassemia syndromes and (2) structural hemoglobin variants (abnormal hemoglobin). Both are caused by mutations and/or deletions in the α or β globin genes. When defective hemoglobin genes cause disruption in the synthesis of hemoglobin with a normal hemoglobin structure, this causes thalassemia, but when defective hemoglobin genes cause changes in the hemoglobin structure, this causes abnormal hemoglobin variants.

Characterization of suspected Hb fractions [22]. As mentioned earlier, common Hb variants are detected with high specificity, as they are the most frequently found variants. However, in reality, several common or uncommon variants may be found within what is called the specific “window” for Hb variants [23].

4. Conclusion

Investigations into hemoglobinopathies in patients with Diabetes Mellitus indicate that hemoglobin gel electrophoresis is a rapid and simple method that allows for the quantitative analysis of the proportions of various hemoglobin bands present. Hemoglobin gel electrophoresis is a simple and convenient technique for studying hemoglobinopathies in patients with Diabetes Mellitus with fasting glucose levels < 200 mg/dL, levels of 200-400 mg/dL, and levels > 400 mg/dL, as well as their HbA1c levels and the position of hemoglobin bands at various fasting glucose levels [24].

Article Information

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Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence): The author(s) hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc.), and text-to-image generators have been used during writing or editing of manuscripts.

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